

Seed morphological and wood anatomical traits reveal diversity of *Garcinia kola* Heckel in tropical humid forest of Cameroon

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ABSTRACT

This work aimed to investigate the diversity of *Garcinia kola* Heckel was found in the tropical humid forest of Cameroon using morphological traits of seeds and anatomical traits of wood. 1550 accessions of *G. kola* seeds were collected from 31 trees, of which 9 were located in the east region, and 22 were located in the center region. The morphological traits of seeds (weight, length, and diameter) were measured on 50 seeds harvested per tree. The transversal, tangential, and radial sections with a thickness of wood of about 15-30µm were obtained from 15 trees and observed under a light microscope for the characterization of anatomical traits. The anatomical parameters (densities, vessel diameter, fiber and ray length, surface of parenchyma, rays, vessels, fiber) were measured in bright-field microscopy images using the Spectrum software. The mean length of seeds is higher in the East region (3.049±0.22 cm) than in the center (2.92±0.36 cm). Meanwhile, seeds from the center region had the highest diameter (1.590±0.13 cm) and weight (6.045± 1.03 g) compared to seeds from the East region (1.35±0.13 cm and 4.52±1.04 g). The high values of anatomical parameters evaluated were observed in the individual originating from the East region. The direct hierarchical classification of the accessions allowed obtaining 2 different groups based on morphological descriptors of seeds and anatomical parameters of woods. The morphological variations of bitter kola seeds and anatomical parameters may have resulted from complex genetic inter-crossing processes and probably the ecological conditions of the zones.

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Introduction

Garcinia kola (commonly called bitter cola) belongs to the Clusiaceae (Guttiferae) family. The species is endemic to the humid lowlands' rainforest ecosystem of West and Central Africa from Sierra Leone to the Democratic Republic of Congo, where natural conditions favor its growth and development. In Cameroon, the species is found in the lowland forests of the Southern part of the country. Bitter kola plays a major role in household therapy, in traditional ceremonies, and is socio-economic and produces good-quality timber and non-timber forest products (Anegbeh et al., 2006; Dah-Nouvlessounon et al., 2016; Kour et al., 2018; Kamga et al., 2019). The nuts have high nutritional values and are widely used as stimulants and aphrodisiacs, as well as facilitating digestion (Kamga et al., 2019; Manourova et al., 2023). The fruits, nuts and bark have been used for centuries in folk medicine to treat ailments from coughs to fevers (Anegbeh et al., 2006; Kamga et al., 2019; Yogom et al., 2020; Manourova et al., 2022). All parts of Bitter kola (from the top to the root) are used by local population in tropical area (Komenan et al., 2019). It, therefore, provides many services to a large part of the rural population and provides an additional source of income (Awono et al., 2013; Komenan et al., 2019; Kamga et al., 2019; Yogom et al., 2020; Manourova et al., 2022). The high demand for the species coupled with unsustainable exploitation has led to the depletion of the species in its natural forest habitat (Dadjo et al., 2020). The species is thus vulnerable and would be facing a high risk of extinction in the wild in the medium-term future (IUCN 2023; Matig et al., 2006; Termote et al., 2012). *G. kola* is also listed as a priority species for immediate conservation actions in the Sub-Saharan Forest Genetic Resources (SAFOGEN) program, due to permanent human pressure because it is multipurpose (Komenan et al., 2019). Despite its socio-economic and cultural values, few attentions were given to *G. kola* and consequently little information is available on the species, indicating the necessity to carry out research studies on this specie. A significant tree-to-tree variation in *G. kola* seeds responses to dormancy-breaking treatments has been reported and suspected to be due to the existence of variability within the species (Kanmegne & Omokolo, 2008). According to the same authors, the morphological parameters of seeds varied within accessions originating from the same location, indicating that these variations may be attributed to genetic characteristics of trees rather than topographic or climatic characteristics of locations. The morphological variation on seeds and fruit in *G. kola* remains scarce, due to lack of data, especially low number of accessions.

Ecological wood anatomy has gained some momentum in recent years (Carlquist 1975, 1977, 1980; Bass et al., 1983; Lehnebach, 2012). There is an abundant documentation on wood anatomy in temperate zone. However, detailed studies of wood structure and especially of tropical wood properties are very scarce and only deal with certain genera and species (Schnitzer & Bongers, 2011; Lehnebach, 2012). There is little information on the general structure of tropical trees, whether it is relatively uniform or diversified, and if it is subject to environmental factors. In addition, knowledge about the wood properties and structure of certain families and a comparison of wood structure are used for identification (Herendeen & Miller, 2000; Schnitzer & Bongers, 2011; Lehnebach, 2012). This area of investigation on the structure of wood properties could provide more information's which can be used by the forest ecologists, environmental botanists and bark anatomists. The wood properties of *G. kola* have never been explored. Wood anatomy is an important source of systematically informative character information that is used for example, in cladistic phylo genetic analyses of relationships in flowering plants. In tropical regions, there is little information on (1) indigenous perception of qualitative or size group morphological variation, within the species, (2) anatomical traits of specific species and (3) establishing a difference between specie using anatomical traits of wood.

The variability of plant species is generally expressed in terms of the characteristics of the plant's vegetative and/or reproductive apparatus (Mars & Marrakchi, 2000). For Dosba et al. (1998), varietal characterisation should concern individuals that have adapted to specific ecological conditions. According to Sounigo et al. (1997) and Zhang (2002), description is necessary for all plant breeding and selection activities, as it makes it possible (i) to target the morphological descriptors of interest and (ii) to identify those that are linked to environmental factors. Several studies have shown that the successful domestication of a species depends on mastery of its morphological characteristics related to fruit, leaves, and wood, because domestication should lead to the species being used in home gardens, production orchards, private woodlots and local and state forests (Kouyaté, 2002, 2005; Ouédraogo, 1995; Diallo, 2001; Mapongmetsem et al., 2011). Also, the success of the restoration of wild species stands necessarily requires control of their morphological characters (Kouyate, 2005). The identification of morphological traits is the first step in the domestication of fruit trees (Leakey, 2019). This view is in line with that of Hoyt (1992), according to whom the conservation of a wild species in situ first requires sampling and comparison of its genetic diversity throughout its geographical and ecological range to domesticate it. Moreover, information regarding the

morphological traits of seeds and the anatomical traits of *G. kola* is far from complete. Several questions remain unanswered, particularly regarding the structuring, distribution, and variability of *G. kola* Heckel. 1) Therefore, this study aims to understand if there is an established folk classification of bitter kola morphotypes. 2) to know if the morphological properties of wood confirm different morphotypes? And which ecological factors drive the pattern of morphological variability in bitter kola? These will be answered by a multidisciplinary approach using morphological parameters of the seed and anatomical characteristics. The general purpose of this work is to (1) describe the variation in *G. kola* seeds based on morphological traits and to (2) describe the anatomical traits of wood collected from different locations.

Materials and Methods

Study area

The study was conducted in Ndikinimeki – Makénéne (Central region) and East region (Figure 1). The area has an equatorial climate with two rainy seasons interspersed by two dry seasons, with a 25 °C average temperature. This zone is characterized by many types of vegetation, such as the Atlantic forest rich in Caesalpiniaceae, the semi-deciduous forest with Sterculiaceae, and Ulmaceae and Semi-deciduous forests with *Terminalia glaucescens* (Letouzey 1985). In the East region, this study was focused on different villages (Lomié, Ngoila, Aschi, Dounzoh, Mpane kobera). The East has a wet equatorial climate, with an average mean temperature of 24°C. Humidity and cloud observed in this region are relatively high, and precipitation averages 1500–2000 mm per year. In this area, the forest formations on firm ground belong to the semi-deciduous forest sector of the dense semi-deciduous Guineo-Congolese. A rain forest characterized by two types of forest formations: Semi-deciduous at Sterculiaceae and Ulmaceae forests and mixed forests, Semi-deciduous and evergreen forests of Dja, with predominantly elements of deciduous forest. Table 1 summarizes the ecological characteristics of the two study sites.

Table 1. Climatic characteristics of the Central and East Region of Cameroon

Features	Central region	East region
Average rainfall (mm)	1200-2000	1500-2000
Temperature range (°C)	23.9°- 26.4°	18°- 30°
Relative humidity range (%)	40 - 86	85 - 98

Climate type	Equatorial	Guinean and Soudanian
Soil type	Red and Yellow ferralitic, Humiferous	Red colluvial ferralitic, Hydromorphic

Figure 1. Location of the study area in the different regions

Seed collection and morphological trait characterization

The local community has indigenous knowledge, which helps to distinguish the morphological variation of bitter cola seeds from different localities. A total of 1550 seeds were collected from 31 trees in different locations, 9 from the east and 22 from the center. From each tree, 50 seeds were collected respectively in the East and Centre regions. The unequal number of trees selected per zone is due to their accessibility, and tree density, which varies between the sites, probably linked to the ecology of species or to over-exploitation in some areas (Kamga et al., 2018). The morphological descriptors of seeds (such as length, width) were measured using a calliper-square graduated to 0.1 mm, and its mass was weighed by balance (Sartorius Basic), as described by Nehemie Sanonne and Denis, (2000).

Figure 2. Measured morphological descriptor of *Garcinia kola* seeds; (A) Weight; (B) length

Characterization of wood anatomical traits

For the anatomical analysis, 15 wood samples were collected in the field (9 from the center and 6 from the east). The number of trees per site was determined by the availability of individuals with a dbh ≥ 10 cm were density of *G. kola* per hectare, is relatively low (van Dijk ,1995; Doucet & Koufani, 1997 ; Kanga et al., 2018). Each sample is a block with at least 1 cm in the tangential direction, 5 cm in the radial direction (bark, phloem, cambial zone, heartwood) and 10 cm in the longitudinal direction removed from the trunk at 1.30 m above the ground level. To be able to keep intact, the cambial zone samples were plunged into a mixture of one-third ethanol, one-third glycerin and one-third water. For those samples, 371 sections (average of 24.19 ± 2.35 sections per individual), with a thickness of about 15-30 μ m were obtained using a sliding microtome (Shenkung Dapples, Mikrot L- serie 1117, Switzerland) and contained phloem, cambial zone, and secondary xylem. The sections were stained with 0.1% safranin O (Merck KgaA, Darmstadt, Germany) solution. They were dehydrated in an ethanol series (50% for 10 minutes, 75% for 5 minutes, and 100% for 10 minutes) (Table 2). Afterwards, the sections were mounted immediately on a slide by using Eukitt and fixed with magnets on aluminum foil to be dried in open air. The observations were made under a light microscope (model N-800M), equipped with a camera, which allowed to obtaining of digital images. The double staining was carried out to be able to differentiate the cell walls in terms of color under a photonic microscope (Dié et al., 2012; Momo et al., 2017).

Densities and diameter of vessels, ray length, surface occupied by parenchyma, rays, vessels, and fiber were measured in bright-field microscopy images using Spectrum software (Soft Imaging System GmbH, Münster, Germany). For these parameters, more than 20 vessels per sample were measured. All characters were described using the IAWA (International Association of Wood Anatomists) List of Microscopic Features for Hardwood Identification

(IAWA Committee, 1989). In the wood, the density of the vessels in a surface of 1 mm² was calculated, the diameter of the vessels (on a slide, at least more than 20 vessels per sample were measured), the area occupied by the vessels, fibers, parenchyma, and rays were determined (Delvaux et al., 2013; Momo et al., 2016; Momo et al., 2017).

Statistical analysis of data

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed using the XLSAT software to assess variation between accessions for morphological descriptors of seeds and anatomical parameters. Significantly different means were separated using Newman-Keuls Multiple Range tests ($p \leq 0.05$). The coefficient of variation was calculated using the XLSAT software version 2017.1, to evaluate the variability between and within populations. Classes of variation are constituted using a scale proposed and tested by Ouédraogo (1995) and used by Kouyaté & Van Damme (2002) when studying the biosystematics of West African *P. biglobosa*: (1) low variation (CV=0-10%); (2) medium variation (CV=10-15%); (3) fairly high variation (CV=15-44%); and (4) high variation (CV>44%). To establish relationships among individual accessions, a dendrogram was generated by hierarchical cluster classification based on quantitative morphological traits of seeds and anatomical parameters of wood.

Results

Morphological traits

Table 2 shows that a Morphological trait varies within and between individuals in different or the same localities. Analysis of variance showed significant variation among *G. kola* individuals and populations for each parameter. There were also significant differences among seed samples originating from the same ecological zone, like YK9EC and YK7EC, for example. Means ranged from 3.64 to 8.9 g for weight, from 2.44 to 3.41 cm for length, and from 1.36 to 1.84 cm for diameter.

Table 2. Variation of morphological traits between *G. kola* individuals

Individuals	Zone	Length (cm)	Diameter (cm)	Weigth (g)
trees				
YK12CC	Centre	3.41±0.11a	1.67±0.08 ab	7.64± 0.64abcd
YK18CC	Centre	3.12±0.27ab	1.79± 0.15a	7.79± 1.63abc
YK19CC	Centre	3.15± 0.22ab	1.63± 0.16abc	6.85± 1.05cdef
YK22CC	Centre	2.93± 0.29bc	1.7± 0.2ab	7.13±1.82 bcdef
YK13CC	Centre	3.29± 0.19ab	1.56±0.1 bcde	6.67± 0.82cdefg

YK17CC	Centre	2.98± 0.28bc	1.64± 0.13abc	6.46± 1.03cdefgh
YK26CC	Centre	3.01± 0.27abc	1.62±0.11 abcd	6.20± 1.06cdefghi
YK10CC	Centre	2.71±0.18 cd	1.69± 0.09ab	5.63±0.59 fghij
YK24CC	Centre	3.01± 0.19abc	1.58±0.06 abcde	6.24± 0.44cdefghi
YK01CC	Centre	3.28± 0.19ab	1.41± 0.19ef	5.96± 1.45defghij
YK23CC	Centre	3.01± 0.27abc	1.53±0.11 bcdef	5.82± 0.92efghij
YK15CC	Centre	2.48± 0.25d	1.65± 0.11abc	4.94± 0.68hijkl
YK14CC	Centre	2.58± 0.22d	1.59±0.12 abcde	5.50±1.04 fghijk
YK07CC	Centre	3.06± 0.32abc	1.43± 0.14def	4.88±1.65 hijkl
YK25CC	Centre	2.38±0.18d	1.63± 0.13abcd	4.90±1.15hijkl
YK08CC	Centre	3.11± 0.15ab	1.35± 0.1fg	4.54±0.58ijkl
YK11CC	Centre	2.40± 0.1d	1.59± 0.09abcde	4.94± 0.87hijkl
YK03CC	Centre	2.97± 0.14bc	1.36±0.13fg	4.35± 0.57jkl
YK20CC	Centre	2.54± 0.12d	1.49± 0.11bcdef	4.41± 0.45jkl
YK16CC	Centre	2.62± 0.23d	1.42±0.05 ef	4.40±0.57 jkl
YK09CC	Centre	2.92±0.16bc	1.25± 0.08g	3.64±0.52 l
YK21CC	Centre	2.45± 0.11d	1.42± 0.06ef	3.85± 0.27kl
YK8EC	East	3.4 ±0.15a	1.76±0.075 a	8.9±0.65 a
YK1EC	East	3.4 ±0.09a	1.61± 0.11ab	8.46±0.94ab
YK4EC	East	3.38±0.33 a	1.69± 0.08ab	7.36±1.4 bcde
YK6EC	East	3.32±0.17 ab	1.67± 0.11ab	7.56±0.85 abcd
YK9EC	East	3.13± 0.28ab	1.62±0.12 abcd	6.90± 1.35cdef
YK7EC	East	2.92± 0.4bc	1.64±0.16 abc	6.74± 1.68cdef
YK2EC	East	3.07± 0.25abc	1.49±0.1 bcdef	6.15± 0.94cdefghi
YK5EC	East	2.35± 0.2d	1.60±0.05 abcde	5.08± 1.03ghijkl
YK3EC	East	2.563 ±0.18d	1.46±0.13cdef	4.640.65±ijkl

Each value represents Mean±SE of n=50 seeds. Within the same column, means with same letter (s) attached are not significantly different at 5% level (Student-Newman-Keuls).

Overall, the mean length of seeds is higher in the East region (3.049±0.22 cm) than in the center (2.92±0.36 cm), Mean while, seeds from the center region had the highest diameter (1.590±0.13 cm) and weight (6.045± 1.03 g) compared to seeds from the East region

(1.35 ± 0.13 cm and 4.52 ± 1.04 g). Analysis of variance showed significant variation between the two populations for this parameter. Intra-variation is low in the East (CV=8.79%), In contrast to the Central population (CV=14.31%) for the seeds' length (Table 3). The seed diameter of the sampled populations averaged 1.47 ± 0.17 cm in length. The maximum values of seed Diameter and weight are observed in the center (1.59 ± 0.13 cm; 6.045 ± 1.3 g). Intra-population variation is average, but remains higher in the Eastern population (CV=11.62%) and low in the Center (CV=10.22%) for the diameter variable (table 4). On the other hand, the intra-population variation is quite high (>15%). This value of the coefficient of variation is higher in the Eastern populations (CV=30.79%) for the weight parameter. The statistical analysis shows a significant difference at the 5% significance level between the seed parameters of the studied stands. The ratio between the length and thickness of the seeds of the studied area populations is 1.92 ± 0.30 . This ratio gives an idea about the shape of the seeds. From the seed measurements, it appears that: (1) the Central population is characterized by larger and shorter seeds, and (2) the Eastern population, is characterized by lighter, smaller seeds. Seeds also show variable morphological diversity. The most common seed shapes were Ellipsoid, Elongated, Spheroid and Oblong (Figure 3).

Table 3. Coefficient of variation of morphological traits within and between *G. kola* populations (n=1550)

Populations	Coefficient of variation (CV; %)		
	Length (cm)	Weigth (g)	Diameter (cm)
PCC	14,31	27,50	10,22
PEC	8,79	30,79	11,62
Average	13,42	28	11,45

Figure 3. The most common shapes of *G. kola* seeds: (A and B)

Anatomical parameters of Bitter kola wood

The general structure of the cross-section of *G. kola* wood does not vary according to the zones. Figure 4 presents the anatomical characteristics of *G. kola* wood collected in the rainforests of Cameroon in cross-section. The arrangement of the vessels does not vary according to the zones. We can observe that the vessels do not have a particular arrangement and have a circular contour. The parenchyma is axial, staggered, and thicker than three cells. It is observed that the rays of the wood are two different sizes; these rays are multiseriated and may consist of two to three cells. We also note the absence of false rays. The characterization of wood, like that of other species of tropical humid forests, is a set of processes consisting in determining the anatomical characteristics of the cells that make up the wood.

Figure 4. (a) An overview of the transversal section of *Garcinia kola* (40x) and (b): Tangential section of the wood of individual YK029 (from the east region) (40x).

Growth rings: 1: They are clearly visible and distinct

Vessels: 5: In the vessels, the pores were disseminated or diffuse; Vessels partly solitary, partly in radial multiples of 2-4; 8' did not have a particular arrangement and had a circular contour, 9' : adjoined (isolated and adjoined mixed or exclusively adjoined) ; absence of features 6, 7, 8, and 9; 13: the type of perforation was simple; 41: the tangential diameter of the vessels was average and varied from 75 to 79 μm ; 45 ': Presence of vessels of two distinct sizes; 47: the vessels were few 8-12 per mm.

Fiber: 66 ': non-septate fibers present; 67: parenchyma-like fiber bands alternating with ordinary fibers; 70: fibers very thick-walled.

Parenchyma: 76: axial parenchyma diffuse; 78: axial parenchyma scanty paratracheal 80: axial parenchyma aliform; 82: axial parenchyma winged-aliform; 83: axial parenchyma confluent; 85: the parenchyma was thicker, more than three cells; 86: Axial parenchyma in narrow bands or lines up to three cells wide; 92: Four (3-4) cells per parenchyma strand.

Rays: 97: Rays 1–3 cells; 101 ': Absence of false rays; 102': the Length of Rays is up to 500 μm ; 103. Rays of the wood were two different sizes: 105: All ray cells upright and/or square; 108: Body ray cells procumbent with over 4 rows of upright and/or square marginal cells; 110': Absence of bordering cells; 115: Rays per millimeter: Number of rays on tangential section per mm: 4-12. However, the length, surface, and diameter of all characters measured in this study and the density of vessels vary within and between populations.

Table 4 shows that the quantitative anatomical traits varied within and between individuals. The high value of different parameters evaluated were observed from the individual (YK012, YK014, YK016, YK017, YK018, YK029), originating from the East region of Cameroon. Analysis of variance showed significant variation among the individuals originated from the same or different regions for these parameters (Table 4). There were also significant differences among wood samples originating from the same ecological zone. Means ranged from 41.52 to 110.76 μm for diameter of vessels, from 2096.41 to 17532.67 μm^2 for the surface occupied by vessel, from 10086.34 to 160584.61 μm^2 for surface occupied by fibers, for 3939.84 to 51872.0 μm^2 for surface occupied by rays, from 138.99 to 520 μm for length of rays, from 8424.4 to 36997.12 μm^2 for surface of parenchyma, and from 5.27 to 18.83 for density of vessels per mm^2 . Analysis of variance showed significant variation among the populations for some parameters (Mean of tangential diameter of vessel (μm^2), Surface occupied by vessels (μm^2), Surface occupied by parenchyma (μm^2), Density of vessels (mm^2)).

The average vessel density varies according to the populations. It is higher in the East, with an average density of 12.68 ± 5.17 vessels per mm^2 and lower in the Center (8.35 ± 2.62 vessels per mm^2). The CV values observed within the populations show a fairly large variation (Tableau 5). This intra-population variation is also quite important between the studied stands (CV=31.59%), but remains higher in the Center (CV=39.25%). On the other hand, the diameter and surface area of the vessels are higher in the Center ($81.73 \pm 16,47$ μm ; $8169,20 \pm 3097,51$ μm^2). However, the intra-population variation is higher in the East (CV=79.26%). The average length of the rays (300.37 ± 121.80 μm), the surface of the rays ($8985,29 \pm 4417,27$ μm^2), the surface of fibers ($18299,60 \pm 10386,03$ μm^2) and the surface of the parenchyma ($16805,98 \pm 9583,84$ μm^2) measured remain low in the Center. However, the intra-population variation is higher in the Center (CV=51.88%), but this variation also remains important between the studied stands (CV=49.08%) for the length of the rays. The statistical analysis (*Student-Newman-Keuls*) performed at the 5% significance level shows that there is a significant difference between the Center and Eastern populations stands for the variables' vessel density, and parenchyma surface ($p < 0.05$). From the measurement made on wood samples, it appears that: (1) the accessions from the Center are characterized by a low density of vessels per mm^2 , a low surface area of rays, fibers and the lowest length of rays; (2) the accessions from the East are characterized by the highest density of vessels per mm^2 and the surface area occupied by parenchyma is the most important. The results of this study, which deals with the anatomical characters of the wood, are of considerable contribution, as they will help to strengthen the criteria for the botanical description of the species.

Table 4. Value of quantitative anatomical parameters of *G. kola* wood from different locations

Samples	Mean of tangential diameter of vessel (μm)	Surface occupied by vessels (μm^2)	Surface occupied by fibers (μm^2)	Surface occupied by rays (μm^2)	Length of Rays (μm)	Surface occupied by parenchyma (μm^2)	Density of vessels (mm^2)
YK017	110.76 \pm 20.1a	17532.67 \pm 3927.95a	22190.0 \pm 18571.11 bc	19145.66 \pm 5167.31bc	520.012 \pm 124.24a	27533.863 \pm 4692.34ab	8.538 \pm 2.85 cde
YK054	90.901 \pm 17.67ab	8846.6 \pm 3450.2b	31513.40 \pm 13698.66b	22009.12 \pm 10023.27b	455.43 \pm 148.46ab	24127.68 \pm 15025.04ab	9.417 \pm 2.18cde
YK083	86.88 \pm 14.28bc	9945.74 \pm 2820.41b	20128.14 \pm 14859.72bc	11167.11 \pm 3886.9bcd	372.13 \pm 141.03abc	13576.07 \pm 5837.16 b	6.91 \pm 2.4de
YK080	94.95 \pm 3.96ab	13554.13 \pm 1279.00a	31969.28 \pm 8696.96 b	4373.23 \pm 3112.78d	196.83 \pm 124.28 cd	19166.40 \pm 18134.34ab	5.27 \pm 0.5 e
YK016	66.35 \pm 16.65cde	6668.50 \pm 3436.84bc	160584.62 \pm 39510.31a	51872.00 \pm 20916.2a	138.99 \pm 120.47d	23470.39 \pm 3292.48ab	8.14 \pm 1.72cde
YK082	93.48 \pm 14.89ab	9673.87 \pm 2920.89b	18994.92 \pm 9040.17bc	6952.96 \pm 4326.87d	225.12 \pm 124.95cd	18968.59 \pm 19592.35ab	6.67 \pm 1.45de
YK012	48.354 \pm 12.35ef	2290.05 \pm 472.52d	17802.24 \pm 10788.1bc	11917.95 \pm 3809.68bcd	469.33 \pm 147.61ab	21375.49 \pm 5970.5ab	13.98 \pm 5.4 b
YK81	78.97 \pm 9.67bcd	7873.98 \pm 2005.72bc	14924.22 \pm 7573.82c	10768.64 \pm 3343.36bcd	313.17 \pm 97.73abcd	13295.71 \pm 4585.18b	7.345 \pm 1.32cde
YK029	87.05 \pm 22.83bc	7668.80 \pm 3414.33bc	8978.88 \pm 11005.61 c	10493.12 \pm 5254.13bcd	357.96 \pm 122.26abc	13167.04 \pm 2344.53 b	12.15 \pm 3.88bc
YK014	76.45 \pm 17.99bcd	5952.40 \pm 1677.08 c	23065.76 \pm 11446.09bc	9784.52 \pm 5159.77cd	299.78 \pm 80.09bcd	14914.12 \pm 6443.93b	18.83 \pm 4.47a
YK050	80.66 \pm 14.91bcd	7113.93 \pm 2246.03 bc	13300.78 \pm 6494.55 c	10303.99 \pm 4570.38 cd	316.79 \pm 129.08abcd	9992.65 \pm 3768.31 b	9.379 \pm 2.73cde
YK061	84.93 \pm 14.28bcd	8165.0 \pm 2711.47bc	10086.34 \pm 6523.14c	8570.76 \pm 3346.64d	286.29 \pm 97.51bcd	11486.19 \pm 5765.25b	9.42 \pm 2.76cde
YK018	41.52 \pm 8.27f	2096.41 \pm 445.78d	9277.10 \pm 4455.05c	8566.85 \pm 4424.01d	344.15 \pm 134.7abcd	36997.12 \pm 33425.3a	8.09 \pm 1.76cde
YK043	62.14 \pm 11.31def	4371.84 \pm 1162.85 cd	16780.93 \pm 10057.12bc	3939.84 \pm 3326.9d	231.47 \pm 76.51cd	18244.35 \pm 6384.79ab	5.65 \pm 1.32de
YK070	74.95 \pm 11.71 bcd	6814.76 \pm 1667.88bc	13936.88 \pm 5951.3c	6604.04 \pm 2725.03d	286.64 \pm 73.02bcd	8424.4 \pm 3787.29b	11.78 \pm 3.32bcd

Within the same column, means with same letter (s) attached are not significantly different at 5% level (Student-Newman-Keuls).

Table 5. Coefficient of variation of anatomical traits within and between *G. kola* population

Populations	Coefficient of variation (CV; %)						
	Density of vessels (mm)	Mean of tangential diameter of vessel (μm^2)	Mean Surface occupied by vessels (μm^2)	(Surface occupied by rays (μm^2))	Length of Rays (μm)	Surface occupied by parenchyma (μm^2)	Surface occupied by fibers (μm^2)
PopEC	23,93	47,17	79,26	100	47,74	100	100
PopCC	39,25	24,86	46,13	70,56	51,88	94,28	86,38
Between	31,59	36,015	62,69	85,28	49,81	100	93,19

Cluster Classification

Ascendant Hierarchical Classification (AHC) based on anatomical parameters of woods and morphological descriptors of seeds shows 2 groups (Figure 5b). Globally, group I is composed of individuals originated from the Center region, characterized by high values of anatomical parameters. The diameter and weight of bitter kola seeds are higher in this population as compared to those of the Eastern region. For example, the surfaces occupied by fibers, rays and parenchyma within the individual from this region are high compared to those sampling from the Center region. One individual originating from the East region (YK014) is present in this group. The Surface occupied by fibers, rays, and parenchyma of woods of this individual is closed to those observed within the individual originated from the center region of Cameroon. Group 2 is mainly composed of individuals originating from the East region with high lengths of seeds. However, two individuals from the center region (YK070, YK050) are present in this group, the fall into the same subgroup as YK029 (from the Eastern region). Analysis of variance indicated that there is no significant variation among these individuals for anatomical parameters. Analysis of variance showed significant variation between the two populations for these morphological descriptors of seeds between these two populations (Table 4). Some seeds harvested on certain individuals from the Eastern region are morphologically closed to those of the Center region. These indicate the presence of some individuals originated from both regions in two groups.

Figure 5. Ascendant Hierarchical classification of *G. kola* based of woods anatomical parameters (A) and seeds morphological descriptors (B)

Correlation matrix between geographical coordinates and wood anatomical traits

Significant and positive correlations were observed between diameter and surface area of the vessel ($r = 0.92$; p value < 0.0001), fiber surface area and comb surface area ($r = 0.73$; p value < 0.0001) (Table 6). Positive correlations were also observed between fiber surface area and spoke length ($r = 0.30$; p value < 0.0001). Surface occupied by fibers, surface occupied by rays, and density of vessels were found to be significantly and negatively correlated with latitude ($r = -0.62$, $r = -0.38$, and $r = -0.34$). This suggests that the surface area of fibers and rays is inversely proportional to latitude. This indicates that these two descriptors increase when the latitude is low. On the other hand, positive correlations were observed between longitude, density of vessels per mm² ($r = 0.51$), fiber surface area ($r = 0.39$), and surface of parenchyma ($r = 0.34$), and between altitude, diameter of vessel ($r = 0.51$), and surface occupied by vessels ($r = 0.28$). Significant positive correlations were also observed between the diameter of the vessel, the surface occupied by vessels, and latitude ($0.22 < r < 0.25$). This indicates that these two descriptors increase with latitude and altitude. Significantly negative correlations were also observed between vessel diameter ($r = -0.14$), vessel surface ($r = -0.28$), and longitude. This seems to indicate that these anatomical features are inversely proportional to longitude.

Table 6. Correlations between geographical coordinates and anatomical descriptors of *Garcinia kola* wood.

Variables	Altitude	Latitude	Longitude	DIAMV	SURFVAI	SURFFIB	SURFRAY	LonguRay	SurfPare	DENSV
Altitude	1									
Latitude	0.777	1								
Longitude	-0.775	-0.993	1							
DIAMV	0.558	0.169	-0.149	1						
SURFVAI	0.636	0.297	-0.283	0.929	1					
SURFFIB	-0.201	-0.361	0.396	0.411	0.398	1				
SURFRAY	-0.144	-0.316	0.346	0.179	0.188	0.738	1			
LonguRay	-0.313	-0.296	0.257	-0.076	-0.109	0.346	0.200	1		
SurfPare	-0.218	-0.311	0.341	-0.168	-0.050	0.161	0.108	0.182	1	
DENSV	-0.600	-0.522	0.511	-0.199	-0.391	-0.003	-0.018	0.331	-0.356	1

NB: Values in bold indicate variables between which there is a strong correlations at the 5% level, With DIAMV (Mean of tangential diameter of vessels), SURFVAI (Mean Surface occupied by vessels), SURFFIB (Surface occupied by fibers), SURFRAY (Surface occupied by rays), LonguRay (Length of Rays), SurfPare (Surface occupied by parenchyma), DENSV (Density of vessels)(mm²).

Discussion

This paper quantifies variation in morphology and anatomical characteristics of *G. kola*, and provides basic knowledge on the level of variation of several quantitative descriptors within and between locations. The mean length of seeds is higher in the East region (>3 cm) than in the center. Meanwhile, seeds from the center region had the highest diameter (> 1.5 cm) and weight (>6 g). The above parameters also significantly varied within individuals originating from the same location and between populations from different ecological zones. The quantitative morphological traits of seeds can be explained by the variability of the genetic diversity of seeds from different populations. The above parameters also significantly varied within accessions originating from the same location, indicating that these variations may be attributed to genetic characteristics of trees rather than topographic or climatic characteristics of locations. The same result has been reported by Kanmegne et al. (2010). According to these authors, the morphological variations of Bitter kola seeds may have resulted from complex genetic intercrossing processes. Generally, the quantitative morphological seed traits showed significant variation between the two populations. These differences in morphological traits of seeds observed between both two populations tend to explain that the two populations are distinct and could correspond to two ecotypes. This differentiation between the two populations can also be explained by the ecological gradient. The ecological variability can lead to the isolation of populations and facilitate their adaptation to local ecological conditions. Isolation of a species in these conditions can interrupt gene flow between different populations. Adaptation to different environments (habitats) leads to the evolution of reproductive isolation and consequently ecological speciation (Schluter et al., 2000; Rundle et al., 2005; Rasanen and Hendry, 2008; Schluter 2009). More specifically, divergent selection between environments causes the adaptive divergence of populations, which leads to the evolution of reproductive barriers that decrease, and ultimately cease, gene flow (Bolnick et al., 2007; Nosil 2012). This variability therefore, leads to ecotypic differentiation and the emergence of new ecotypes (Mallet et al. 2009). In the present study, significant differences were found among sites for any seed characteristics that were analyzed. This phenotypic variation is different from that observed by (Kapchie et al., 2002), on fruit and kernels in two populations of *Irvingia gabonensis*. According to these authors, the lack of variability is due to the homogeneity of ecological conditions at the sites that were surveyed (Herendeen & Miller 2000). The broad variability found between and within trees in this study is typical of that found in populations of an outbreeding species, and indicates that extensive phenotypic diversity of seeds exists

within wild stands of *G. kola*. However, according to Mañnourová et al. (2023), the diversity of morphological characteristics of different populations within and between Populations of *G. kola* in Cameroon could be influenced more by genotype than external conditions. Other studies carried out in Côte d'Ivoire on the variability of morphological characteristics of *Adansonia digitata* show a variation in morphological traits according to agro-ecological zones (Kouyaté et al., 2011; Kodjo et al., 2022). According to these authors, humidity seems to have a positive influence on the dimensions of certain traits, such as fruit width, fruit mass and fruit stalk dimensions.

The results of the present study showed that the anatomical characteristics evaluated vary within and between populations of *G. kola*. These variations observed in anatomical traits of wood can be explained by the characteristics of the two study sites linked probably to climatic or edaphic conditions of the locations and suggest that, the two populations are different. The similar study was conducted in tropical areas and mainly in temperate zones on tree barks to distinguish two species or different morphotype. A similar result was obtained by Mbagwu and Unamba, 2011), on *Cola acuminata* and *Cola nitida* in tropical humid forests of Nigeria. The presence of big and numerous vascular bundles with big and many vessels evenly scattered within the root cortex of *Cola acuminata* distinguished this taxon from *Cola nitida* with small and many vessels. According to these authors, the atomic characteristics of roots for these taxa are a good taxonomic character that can distinguish these taxa. The variability of anatomical parameters within taxa could be an ecological adaptation, especially in the manufacturing and storage of food and water for the survival of the plants. According to Carlquist (1975), environmental conditions can affect the bark or wood characteristics. For Nelson and Safou-Tchiama (2015), the difference in vessel density between the wood of individuals of the same species can be explained by the growth conditions associated with the areas of origin. Good growing conditions lead to a reduction in porosity (by reducing the number of vessels per unit area) and an increase in the proportion of fibres (Leclercq 1977; Tsoumis and Panagiotidis, 1980). Herendeen and Miller (2000), add that these environmental conditions prolong the conductivity of conducting tissues, which include sclerification, form of collapse, and form and structure of rays. Keller (1993), studies in temperate zones have shown that ecological and edaphic factors can affect the density of oak wood, vessel size, parenchyma and wood fiber richness. This author observed that, coniferous woods like *Picea abies* (Commun Épicéa) and *Pinus sylvestris* coming from Nordic forests are much more similar compared to woods of the same species growing in a temperate climate. This Nordic

wood is made up of fibers with relatively large cell cavities; probably due to the duration of the seasons and the length of the day. Parsa (1970), indicated that the wood structure of *Fagus orientalis* would be influenced by altitude. According to this author, in the climatic conditions where rainfall is relatively high, evapotranspiration increases with altitude, under the combined effect of a decrease in the voltage of water vapor in the atmosphere. All these conditions are reflected on the woody level by the production of a final wood made up of small vessels and short fibers. Ethnobotanical surveys and the observation of tree phenology in different locations revealed that the two populations were flowering at different periods. Some information obtained in the field indicated that some time there is an overlapping on flowering. Generally, this variation in flowering period suggests a pre-zygotic reproductive barrier, a favorable condition for the isolation of populations and potentially speciation. Although, the perceived qualitative variation could be determined and should not be neglected. The genetic diversity can enable us to understand the ecological variation of this species in the tropical humid forest of Cameroon. To get a more powerful morphological discrimination, quantitative descriptors should hence be combined with locally perceived qualitative traits (Color, taste). Practical conservation measures are to be taken by the forest authority to preserve genetic diversity and maintain the species.

Conclusion

This study has highlighted preliminary required information for morphological and anatomical characteristics of *G. kola* in Cameroon. It demonstrates that different “ecotypes” of Bitter kola are present in Cameroonian forests. This may be recorded by morphological descriptors of seeds and anatomical characteristics of wood. However, more comprehensive research extended to other regions and to other morphological descriptors (seeds, fruit, etc.) is needed for description. The morphological or anatomical descriptors studied here can be good taxonomic characters that can be used to differentiate the much closer species (*Erythrophleum suaveolens* and *E. ivorense*; *Lophira alata* and *L. lanceolata* etc.).

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